

Data Collection Techniques and Evaluation of Project Objectives

Assignment 7

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For this study, the primary data is collected through qualitative method using interview technique. Semi-structured is incorporated in this research design as the researcher believed that open-ended questions were efficient ways for collecting data from the participants of the research as the interviews are conducted in focused group study method (Bryman, 2012). Open-ended questions are considered to enable individual's scope and time for discussing their knowledge, experiences, and perceptions. The inclusion criteria defined for the selection of participants is on the basis of researcher's experience in the medical field.

The instrument used is an interview questionnaire that will consist of six open-ended questions. The instrument will be conducted in an unstructured interview format to complete the study before the data analysis phase of the study. Furthermore, when conducting interviews, questions were added and subtracted and the sequence of questions was also be changed varying from interviewee to interviewee. The change in interview question is possible as there will be focused group study used. In this way a lot of data will be collected and project's objective will be fulfilled.

Reliability, Validity and Applicability

Reliability and Validity ensure the legitimacy of research. Deliberate actions are necessary to establish legitimacy. In qualitative research, validity is equivalent to credibility; reliability is dependability (Bloomberg & Volpe, 2008). To encourage validity and reliability, a focused group study of the instrument took place. A researcher will sit with the group of people

and make the interview session as a discussion. It will help to establish the face validity of the interview questions.

Validity assesses whether the meaning and interpretation of an event is sound or whether a particular measure is an accurate reflection of intent. Many authors have stressed upon checking the validity of research instruments. Furthermore, the use of triangulation design has been used in the study to increase the validity and credibility of the results. Further, the data was collected during the same time frame in order to make it more concurrent and separate to increase the credibility and validity of the research. It ensures the collection of data from all sources. Thus, the validity of the proposed study was accomplished with the use of methodological and data source to determine the study's findings.

In case of applicability, the researcher is the instrument in the current qualitative study (Babbie, 2009). The researcher had pertinent prior experience or background in the medical field successfully. The potential influence of the researcher on the participants during the interview is limited. The researcher will suspend any preconceived notions or personal insights that might unduly influence the dialogue of participants to minimize the researcher bias.

Strategies if Outcomes are not Positive

As with any study, issues may arise that if the outcomes are not positive, including the question of the validity of the research and possible bias on the part of the respondents and/or the researcher. For this the researcher always goes with the validity of the data used from the respondents, so for this researcher should assure following types of validity for positive outcomes. The first type is descriptive validity, the initial concern of most qualitative researchers is adherence to the facts of their case, which is to say, that they are not distorting or making up

facts in the data collection process. This also means leaving items out as well as reporting accurately the items that they observe. A second type of validity, that Maxwell describes, is interpretative. This validity is concerned with the perceptions and true meaning of the information that was gathered from the respondents. The third type is labeled theoretical validity, one the researcher makes sure about the validity issue, the outcomes turns out to be appropriate and positive as the data collected is valid.

Implication of Practice

This research will be helpful for the researcher conducting a similar study in different hospitals of various cities. The positive result of this study will increase the treatment/test method; whereas, the negative results may give a reason for the medical professionals/official to focus on the redevelopment efforts that will lead to the positive effect in the long-run.

Future Research

A recommendation for future research would be to take a sustainable code, principle, or guideline and apply the method to a suitable area of type 2 diabetes patients. In addition, further research could include an applied project utilizing a measurement application and applying the best treatment for type 2 diabetes patient. What can be measured can be managed through exercise, and what can be managed can create awareness, education, and transparency for both patient and doctor, and as the process suggests, it is for complete betterment of patient.

References

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Bryman, A. (2012). Social research methods. *Oxford university press*.